

The Inconsistencies In The Exodus Narrative: An Investigation Into The Number of Midwives and the Number of Israelites

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Abstract

In this study, the demographic contradiction in the biblical narrative of the number of Israelites in Egypt during Moses' birth (Exodus 1:15) has been critically analyzed. Through biblical analysis and historical critique, the study brings into light the impossibility of harmonizing the contention that the Israelites had become hugely populous with the fact that they were attended in childbirth by only two midwives. The results show that if the Israelites were as numerous, then two midwives would have been inadequate, contradicting Exodus 1:15. If only two midwives were required, then the Israelites could not have been as numerous as reported. This inherent contradiction necessitates a rejection of at least one part of the biblical account, raising severe doubts about its historical and demographic validity.

Key Words: Bible, Exodus, Israelites, Midwives, Egypt, Moses

Introduction

In Exodus Verse 1:9, the King of Egypt said to his people that “the Israelites have become far too numerous for us”¹ and in Exodus Verse 1:15 the King of Egypt Ordered (King’s Order) the two Hebrew midwives “When you are helping the Hebrew women during childbirth on the delivery stool, if you see that the baby is a boy, kill him; but if it is a girl, let her live”²

The question arises: was it possible for only two midwives to observe the childbirth of all the Israelites? Previously, the King had expressed apprehension that the Israelites were far too numerous for the Egyptians. These two verses seem unable to coexist logically. The preceding phrase, 'far too numerous,' suggests that the Israelites were significant in number at the time. However, the latter verse implies that their population was so small that only two

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¹Bible Gateway passage: Exodus 1 - New International Version, BIBLE GATEWAY,
<https://www.biblegateway.com/passage/?search=Exodus%201&version=NIV> (last visited Dec 14, 2024).

²*Id.*

midwives could manage them. Furthermore, the names of these two midwives are also provided, which raises doubts about the Bible's account of this part of history.

It is also a historical claim in the Bible, found in Genesis 46:27³ & Exodus 1:5⁴ that all those who came to Egypt from Canaan with Jacob numbered seventy in total. However, based on other verses, such as Exodus 1:7⁵ it is stated that afterward, in Egypt, the Israelites multiplied greatly, increased in numbers, and became so numerous that the land was filled with them. This caused apprehension in the King of Egypt, who ordered the two midwives to kill all newborn male babies of the Israelites. According to Exodus 2:2⁶ this was also the time when Moses was born. Furthermore, Exodus 12:37⁷ claims that when Moses led the Israelites out of Egypt, there were about six hundred thousand men on foot, besides women and children.

If we calculate the total number of Israelites, including women and children, based on Exodus 12:37 and trace this figure back to the time of Moses' birth, we can determine the actual number of Israelites during the King's order. This, in turn, would help us assess whether it was logically feasible for only two midwives to oversee every birth among the Israelites.

Investigation

To investigate the matter, I am deeply grateful to Rabbi Ben Abrahamson, a Rabbinical historian and consultant for the Religious Courts of Israel, who kindly agreed to discuss this point with me. All discussions were conducted electronically and have been edited to correct

³Bible Gateway passage: Genesis 46 - New International Version, BIBLE GATEWAY, <https://www.biblegateway.com/passage/?search=Genesis%2046&version=NIV> (last visited Dec 15, 2024).

⁴Bible Gateway passage: Exodus 1 - New International Version, BIBLE GATEWAY, <https://www.biblegateway.com/passage/?search=Exodus%201&version=NIV> (last visited Dec 15, 2024).

⁵*Id.*

⁶Bible Gateway passage: Exodus 2 - New International Version, BIBLE GATEWAY, <https://www.biblegateway.com/passage/?search=Exodus%202&version=NIV> (last visited Dec 15, 2024).

⁷Bible Gateway passage: Exodus 12 - New International Version, BIBLE GATEWAY, <https://www.biblegateway.com/passage/?search=Exodus%2012&version=NIV> (last visited Dec 15, 2024).

any syntax or grammatical errors while preserving the original text as much as possible. The questions/answers from Rabbi Ben Abrahamson are as follows:

Q-1. What would have been the probable number of children of Israel in Egypt, at the time of the birth of Moses?

A-1 When they left, 80 years later, they were about 600,000. If there are 600,000 people total, assuming a 1:3 male-to-female ratio and a 1:4 adult-to-child ratio, that would be 37,500 males, 112,500 females, and 450,000 children in this scenario.

1522 BCE – Jacob comes down to Egypt

1386 BCE – Birth of Moses

1306 BCE (or 1300 BCE) – The Exodus

This means the time all the Children of Israel spent in Egypt was about 220 years.

They started these years with 70 people and ended with 600,000.

I estimate that, using traditional ratios for ancient civilizations, this 600,000 would break down as

37,500 males, 112,500 females, and 450,000 children.

Q-2. Sir, kindly tell me the most probable number of Israelites when the King ordered the killing of the newborn male children of the Israelites.

A-2 About 2000

Q-3. The population estimates of the Israelites at the time of the birth of Moses in Egypt were around 2000. Am I right?

A-3 That was the number of baby boys.

Q-4. And how many adults were there?

A-4 A: Let me try and calculate this.

Q-5. Ok Waiting

A-5

Year	Number Of Israelites
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1520	210
1510	300
1500	432
1490	621
1480	893
1470	1284
1460	1847
1450	2653
1440	3809
1430	5469
1420	7856
1410	11280
1400	16195
1390	23244
1380	33343
1370	47877
1360	68747
1350	98689
1340	141784
1330	203705
1320	292460
1310	420833
1300	600000

So assuming 1300 BCE was actually 600000 people, then at 1386 BCE (Moses' birth) would have been about 35,000 Israelites.

Q-6. Thanks, so when the King of Egypt ordered the killing of the newborn male of children of Israel, at the same time Israelites were 35000 in number. Am I right?

A-6 Yes. It makes a lot of assumptions, but it's the conclusion given the information available.

In addition, the Honorable Rabbi shared an Excel File too, containing the following data

BCE[1]	Men[3]	Women	Children	Infant	
				Boys	Israelites
1520	67	202	808	17	1,077
1510	102	305	1,221	26	1,628
1500	154	462	1,846	39	2,462
1490	233	698	2,792	60	3,722
1480	352	1,055	4,221	90	5,628
1470	532	1,595	6,382	137	8,509
1460	804	2,412	9,649	206	12,866

1450	1,216	3,648	14,590	312	19,453
1440	1,838	5,515	22,060	472	29,413
1430	2,780	8,339	33,355	713	44,473
1420	4,203	12,608	50,433	1,079	67,243
1410	6,355	19,064	76,254	1,631	101,672
1400	9,608	28,824	115,296	2,466	153,728
1390	14,527	43,582	174,328	3,729	232,437
1380	21,965	65,896	263,583	5,638	351,445
1370	33,212	99,635	398,538	[5]	531,384
1360	50,216	150,647	602,590		803,453
1350	75,926	227,779	911,116		1,214,821
1340	114,801	344,402	1,377,607		1,836,809
1330	173,578	520,735	2,082,942		2,777,256
1320	262,451	787,352	3,149,408		4,199,211
1310	396,825	1,190,476	4,761,905		6,349,206
1300	600,000	1,800,000	7,200,000		9,600,000

Q-7. Genesis 46:27 reads "The members of Jacob's family, which went to Egypt, were **seventy** in all". It is incomprehensible why are you bifurcating them all in Men, Women Children, and Infant Boys culminating in bringing the total number as large as 1000 approx. Please explain.

A-7 The statement "**seventy in all**" is **followed by** a list of their names. It can be seen from that list that there are 67 men and 3 women, which is an unsustainable ratio of men to women. So I apply the "1:3 male-to-female ratio and a 1:4 female-to-child ratio" to the 67 men. This is the standard number used by sociologists for this time period.

For the number in Exodus 12:37, archeologists believe that 600,000 men together with millions of women and children is too large a number. Because in other places, Jewish tradition sees 600,000 as including men, women, and children together, I use the same "1:3 male-to-female ratio and a 1:4 female-to-child ratio" to calculate 37,500 men.

Q-8. So in principle, you agree, irrespective of the debate on sustainability, that as per the Torah, this number was 70. Am I right?

A-8 Yes

Q-9. I did not find any such thing followed by it. (referring to the phrase **followed by** in the preceding answer)

A-9 See verses Genesis 46:10-27, sixty-seven names of men, three names of women

8. And these are the names of the children of Israel who were coming to Egypt: Jacob and his sons Jacob's firstborn was Reuben.

9. And the sons of Reuben were Hanoch and Pallu, Hezron and Carmi.
10. And the sons of Simeon were Jemuel, Jamin, Ohad, Jachin, and Zohar, and Saul the son of the Canaanites.
11. And the sons of Levi were Gershon, Kehath, and Merari.
12. And the sons of Judah were Er, Onan, Shelah, Perez, and Zerah. Now Er and Onan had died in the land of Canaan; and the sons of Perez were Hezron and Hamul.
13. And the sons of Issachar were Tola, Puvvah, Iob, and Shimron.
14. And the sons of Zebulun were Sered, Elon, and Jahleel.
15. These are the sons of Leah, that she bore to Jacob in Padan Aram, and Dinah his daughter. All the souls of his sons and daughters were thirty-three.
16. And the sons of Gad were Ziphion, Haggi, Shuni, and Ezbon, Eri, Arodi, and Areli.
17. And the sons of Asher were Imnah, Ishvah, Ishvi, and Briah, and Serah, their sister; and the sons of Briah were Heber and Malkiel.
18. These are the sons of Zilpah, whom Laban gave to his daughter Leah, and she bore these to Jacob, sixteen souls.
19. The sons of Rachel, Jacob's wife, were Joseph and Benjamin.
20. And to Joseph were born in the land of Egypt, whom Asenath, the daughter of Potiphera, the governor of On, bore to him: Manasseh and Ephraim.
21. And the sons of Benjamin were Bela, Becher, Ashbel, Gera, Na'aman, Ehi, and Rosh, Muppim, Huppim, and Ard.
22. These are the sons of Rachel, who were born to Jacob: all the souls were fourteen.
23. And the sons of Dan: Hushim.
24. And the sons of Naphtali were Jahzeel, Guni, Jezer, and Shillem.
25. These are the sons of Bilhah, whom Laban had given to his daughter Rachel, and she bore these to Jacob, all the souls were seven.
26. All the souls coming to Egypt with Jacob, those descended from him, excluding the wives of Jacob's sons, all the souls were sixty-six.
27. And Joseph's sons, who were born to him in Egypt, two souls; all the souls of the house of Jacob who came to Egypt were seventy.

Q-10. This is not followed by but preceded by Sir

A-10 Yes, you are right. My mistake

Q-11. So these all were seventy, including men, women, and children?

A-11 67 men and 3 women are named. But I assume there must have been more women. Assuming the number of men is exact, and using the standard ratios used by sociologists for that time period, I arrive at 1000, including men, women, and children.

It is possible to not assume, but then the numbers don't work out so well.

Q-12. But these were not all 1000 but 70. The ratio whatsoever you want to apply should be within figure 70. Sir don't assume contrary to the plain text of Torah. I believe in the Torah, not in the assumptions of experts.

A-12 Un-Answered

Q-13. This is copied and pasted from the Bible NIV

26 All those who went to Egypt with Jacob—those who were his direct descendants, **not counting his sons' wives—numbered sixty-six persons.**

27 With the two sons who had been born to Joseph in Egypt, **the members of Jacob's family, which went to Egypt, were seventy in all.**

Both verses contradict each other

A-13 Verse 26 counts the people who left Canaan for Egypt. This did not include Joseph, his two sons or Jocheved who was born on the way.

Q-14. But verse 27 tells that they all were **seventy**

A-14 $66 + \text{Joseph} + \text{Efraim} + \text{Menashe} + \text{Jocheved} = 70$

Q-15. So it's clear that they all were 70 including women and children?

A-15 No.

This is what the text tells us:

Verse 10-25 says 64 men and 2 women left Canaan to go to Egypt.

Verse 26 says 66 people, not including wives, left Canaan to go to Egypt.

Verse 27 says these 66 people, with 3 already there is 70.

The number of wives is not mentioned.

The number of children is not mentioned

Verse 27 does not count Jocheved who was born on the way.

I do not know of any authentic tradition that tells us the number of wives and children. So I resort to science, with estimates of populations at the time.

Q-16. Based on the chart you shared (In the light of Birth of Moses in the year 1386 BCE)

There were 2324437 Israelites in the year 1390

There were 351445 Israelites in the year 1380

This means that there were 119,008 Israelites were increased in these 10 years.
Am I right?

A-16 Yes. the rate of increase grows quickly

Q-17. It means that 11900 Israelites were born in one year
991.73 Israelites born in one month
33.057 Israelites born per day
means more than one birth in every hour
Am I right?

A-17 Yes. During Moses' (PBUH) life, the Children of Israel were growing quite rapidly.

Q-18. If there were the birth of more than one child every hour, then how was it possible for only **two midwives** (Exodus 15-16) to observe the birth and in the case of the birth of a male child, kill him?

A-18 When it says there were two midwives, the Hebrew language can also mean there were two head midwives who supervised others.

Q-19. Please explain how did you deduce that these were two head midwives? If you may, please give some examples from the Torah itself.

A-19 Here are some examples where a noun, like "brothers" or "sons" is used to mean a large group not specifically limited to biological brothers and sons. The same would be true of saying 2 midwives.

Genesis 29:12: Rachel introduces herself to Jacob as "daughter of your father's brother," but Jacob then addresses her as "my sister." This could be an affectionate term within the extended family, hinting at their shared Laban ancestry.

Numbers 26:8: The lineage of Hezron is outlined, mentioning his "sons," some of whom are known from other verses to be his grandsons

Q-20. **Genesis 29:12: Rachel introduces herself to Jacob as "daughter of your father's brother," but Jacob then addresses her as "my sister." This could be an affectionate term within the extended family, hinting at their shared Laban ancestry.**

How does it support your argument? Please explain.

Numbers 26:8: The lineage of Hezron is outlined, mentioning his "sons," some of whom are known from other verses to be his grandsons

This too please in the same manner

- A-20 In Hebrew, inexact, poetic language is sometimes used. Someone who is actually a "cousin", can be called a "sister", really meaning "like a sister". In the case of "two midwives," it can really mean "two midwives that supervise others."
- Q-21. Two midwives can really mean two midwives who supervise others. May be a mere assumption without any factual standing. If it was so then King might have given an order in clear language, ultimately leaving no room to presume something.
- A-21 The king probably gave his order in Egyptian. When Moses (PBUH) wrote the Torah, he chose Hebrew words that would be most understood by the Children of Israel, which may have been different. For example, Moses (PBUH) often talks about the "Children of Israel", but they are not all Israel/Jacob's sons. Some are great-grandsons, others are converts, etc.
- Q-22. I know it would have happened, but my contention is that you are merely relying on your assumptions or presumptions about the issue of two midwives. Isn't it?
- A-22 Every word in every language has a range of meanings. Just like the word "person" means one and "people" means many, yet "sheep" can mean one or many. It is not merely relying on my assumptions or presumptions, but these are the valid range of meanings for these Hebrew words. This is just how the language works.
- Q-23. Honorable friend, I know how language works. I posed the question concerning the issue of **two midwives**, to which you responded with your assumptions. This issue would not matter if there were words **midwives**. The usage of the word **two** signifies that these were **two midwives** only. Simple is that. Hope you understand.
- A-23 Unanswered.

Discussion

The conversation with Rabbi Ben Abrahamson, though informative, shows great inconsistencies in the biblical historical account of events concerning the number of Israelites in Egypt at the time of the Birth of Moses. The fact that the Rabbi relies on assumptions and sociological ratios to reinterpret the plain text of the Torah raises serious questions about the historical integrity of the narrative of the Bible.

Population Counts: The Rabbi's estimates of the Israelites' population when Moses was born, by using sociological models, disagree with the Torah. Although the Torah says that the number at first is 70 (Genesis 46:27), he inflates it to a little over 1,000 by presumed male-to-female and adult-to-child ratios that do not comport with the text of the Torah.

Role of Two Midwives: The Rabbi's explanation that the "two midwives" mentioned in Exodus 1:15 were supervisory figures overseeing others lacks textual evidence from the Torah itself. This interpretation appears to rely on linguistic assumptions rather than concrete scriptural or historical support.

Linguistic and Cultural Assumptions: The Rabbi constantly resorts to cultural and linguistic subtleties to justify his interpretations, such as in examples where Hebrew words are used that have more comprehensive meanings, such as "brothers" to represent a group or "two" as representing leadership. However, these justifications are often specious and not convincing evidence for the historical record.

Birth Rates and Practical Feasibility: If over one Israelite child was born per hour in the lifetime of Moses, as the Rabbi testified to above, then two midwives cannot possibly have handled all births. This alone contradicts the Torah account but does not explain how such a scenario would be realistic.

Inconsistencies in Exegetical Analysis. The Rabbi admits mistakes in his perception of some passages from the Bible, such as Genesis 46:10-27, in which numerical inconsistencies in the sum total of Jacob's family can be seen. Such discrepancies further undermine the defense made for the historicity of the Bible account.

Generally speaking, the Rabbi relies upon inference and reinterpretation for support where sociological models blur instead of interpreting the literal message from the Torah. The facts

came on surface after the discussion may raise questions to the historical soundness of the biblical narration.

Conclusion

In light of the above facts and investigation, it may be safely concluded that the analysis of the biblical account in Exodus reveals a fundamental contradiction when the text is examined through a historical and demographic perspective. The claim that the Israelites had become too numerous when applied to the population ratios of the time challenges the plausibility of only two midwives overseeing the birth of such a large population. If we accept the assertion that the Israelites were indeed numerous, it logically follows that the number of midwives would have to exceed two, contradicting the claim in Exodus 1:15. Conversely, if we accept the presence of only two midwives, we would obviously have to reject the notion that the Israelites were numerous enough. In either case, we are left with a clear rejection of at least one aspect of the biblical narrative, leading to the conclusion that this particular account does not align with historical or demographic reality.